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Association of health status and body condition score in intensively and extensively reared Skopelos dairy goats

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The objective was to study the association between body condition score (BCS) and health conditions (foot- and udder-related issues, digestive, respiratory and systematic diseases, lesions and poor hair coat quality) in goats reared under 2 different farming systems. A total of 133 intensively reared (Farm A, zero-grazing) and 153 extensively reared (Farm B- grazing) purebred Skopelos goats, of the same genetic merit, were randomly selected and subjected to thorough clinical examination for 2 consecutive lactations. Daily milk yield (DMY) was recorded, at post-weaning and every 50 days thereafter. BCS was assessed using a 5-degree scale with 0.25 increments. Mixed linear regression models were developed with the observed health issues, age, farm, stage of lactation, year of assessment, and DMY, being used as fixed effects and the animal as random. The overall average BCS was 3.0 and ranged from 2.8 to 3.2. Poor hair coat quality was associated with a decrease in BCS by 0.09 (CI: -0.054 to -0.121, $p < 0.001$), while the presence of udder abscesses was associated with increased BCS by 0.15 (CI: 0.066 to 0.236, $p < 0.01$). Among the rest studied health issues, none was found to be significantly associated with BCS, despite some observed tendencies. Daily milk yield was negatively associated with BCS ($p < 0.001$) in all cases, but it was increased by approximately 0.1 ($p < 0.01$) degrees in goats of Farm A. Year of assessment ($p < 0.001$), age ($p < 0.05$), and stage of lactation ($p < 0.001$) were also significantly associated with BCS. The observed positive association between poor hair coat quality and BCS implies a common underlying cause. The latter could be used as proxy traits of nutritional and welfare status of dairy goats. The absence of significant associations between specific health issues and BCS is most likely associated with the timely treatment of acute and systematic diseases as well as the good health status of the studied population. This work has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme entitled Code: Re-farm, under grant agreement No101000216.

Session 4

Theatre 5

The relationship between the content of ketone bodies and fatty acids in cow's milk

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The study aimed to explore the relationships between the concentration of ketone bodies (acetone (mACE) and β -hydroxybutyric acid (mBHB)) and selected fatty acids (FA; C14:0, C16:0, C18:0, C18:1) and FA groups (LCFA, MUFA, PUFA, SFA, SCFA, TUFA) in cow milk, analyzed using the FTIR method. Confirming these relationships could improve models for identifying cows with subclinical ketosis (HYKL). The study analyzed around 3 million milk samples from 2017 to 2019, provided by the Polish Federation of Cattle Breeders and Dairy Farmers. The milk samples were collected from Holstein-Friesian cows during test day between the 6th and 60th day of lactation. Spearman's correlation coefficients were used to assess relationships between the milk components. The analysis included milk samples from cows in 1st, 2nd, and ≥ 3 rd lactation groups, as well as healthy (NKL) and HYKL cows. Classification was based on mACE and mBHB concentrations (de Roos et al., 2007): NKL: when mACE < 0.15 mmol/L and mBHB < 0.1 mmol/L; HYKL: when mACE ≥ 0.15 mmol/L or mBHB ≥ 0.1 mmol/L. The correlation coefficient (r) between mACE and mBHB concentrations was 0.78. In contrast, the r values between mACE and SCFA and C14:0 were -0.23 and -0.2, respectively. The strongest relationships were observed between mACE and LCFA and TUFA ($r = 0.49$), as well as C18:1 and C18:0 ($r = 0.48$). The concentrations of these acids were also correlated with mBHB; for LCFA and TUFA, r values were 0.51 and 0.5, respectively. The r values between mBHB and C18:1 and C18:0 were 0.48 and 0.49, respectively. In the NKL group, the correlation between mACE and SCFA and C14:0 was -0.25 and -0.24, respectively, and no significant correlation between mBHB and FA concentrations was observed. In the HYKL group, higher correlation coefficients were observed between mACE and FA concentrations compared to the entire dataset and the NKL group, with the highest $r = 0.55$ for C18:0. Correlation values between mACE, mBHB, and selected milk FA encourage for further research on using FA to predict risk of HYKL.